

Ennayiram Vedic College

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Abstract: A Vishnu temple named Alagiya Narasimha Perumal temple is situated at Ennayiram in Vikravandi taluk of Villupuram district. It was known as Rajaraja Vinnagar. A college which taught Veda was there during the period of Rajendra I. This college was running inside the temple. Totally 340 students had been educated in this college and 14 professors had worked there. Vedas like Rig and Yajur and Sutras like Chandoga-sama, Talavakara-sama, Vajasaneya, Baudhayaniya grihya and kalpa and kathaka were the curriculam followed by the college to teach the students. The professors who worked in this college were given good salary and the students were also given scholarships. Ennayiram Vedic College was one among the popular colleges during the Chola period.

Keywords: Alagiya Narasimha Perumal Temple, Ennayiram, Rajaraja Vinnagar, Rajendracholan *Salai*, Vedic College.

Introduction

The Cholas ruled in Tamil Nadu from 850 A.D. to 1279 A.D. and gave more importance to education in their 430 years of ruling period. They had shown more interest in developing the Tamil language and Vedic Sastras. They established the residential educational institutions provoking the process of excellency of teaching and learning. They had given generous amount of salary to the teachers and they had provided scholarships for the students who had been educated there. It was the most prominent Vedic college in Ennayiram during the Chola period.

Location

Ennayiram village located in Vikravandi taluk in Villupuram district is 15 kilometers away from the west of Perani bus stop in Chennai-Trichy road and 8 kilometers away from the east of Nemur. Nemur is located 20 kilometers to the north from Villupuram in the Villupuram-Gingee road. A temple named Alagiya Narasimha Perumal Temple is located in the center of Ennayiram Village. A college which taught Vedas had been running in this place during the period of Rajendran I.

Historical Background of Ennayiram

The inscription belonging to the period of Rajendra Chola I denotes this place as *Jayangondachola Valanattu Taniyur*, the inscription of Rajathi Raja I denotes it as *Rajendrachola Valanattu Panaiyur Nattu Brahmadeyam Taniyuragiya Rajaraja Chaturvedimangalam*, the inscription belonging to Kulothunga Chola I denotes it as *Gangai Kondachola Valanattu Panaiyur Nattu Brahmadeyam Taniyur Rajaraja Chaturvedimangalam*, the 11th year inscription of Parakesari Tiribuvana Chakaravarthy Rajaraja Deva denotes it as *Rajaraja Valanattu Rajaraja Chaturvedimangalam*, the inscription (Sagam 1461) belonging to the period of Achuda Devamaharaya who was the son of Veera Pratapa Narasinga Devamaharaya denotes this place as *Jayankondachola Mandalathu Pazha Kundra Kottathu Panaiyur Nattu Rajaraja Chaturvedimangalam*.

This place had historical importance as Kavi Kalamegam was born in this place. This place was called by the name Paruthikollai during the Pallava period. Sri Ramanuja visited Paruthikollai while on his way from Sriperumbudur to Tiruvakintapuram. This is the place where Jain monks lived who gave the work *Naladiyar*. As an evidence that this is an ancient place of Jains, thirty five stone beds, five Tamil inscriptions and natural caves which belong to the 9th and 10th century A.D. are there in this place. The Jains who belong to this village Ennayiram were the ones who wrote *Naladiyar* in Madurai during the period of Koon Pandiyan. At that time, the Pandiya king had heavy fever. When the Jain monks have given wrong medicines to him, the minister Kulachirayar and the queen Mangayarkarasi have called Thirugnanasambandar who visited Madurai at that time and had sung *Thiruneetru Pathigam* and gave *Thiruneeru* (holy ash) and then the fever was cured. Pandiya became very happy and he himself converted from Jainism to Shaivism. As per the request of Gnanasambandar, he ordered to process impalement on the eight thousand Jains. This event was called Ennayiram (eight thousand) *Samanarkal Kazhuvetram* in history.

History of the Temple

This place was called Rajaraja chaturvedimangalam during the Chola period. There were many temples in this place such as a Perumal temple and three Lord Shiva temples during the period of Rajendra I. Alagiya Narasimha Perumal temple which was called Rajaraja Vinnagaram is among them. This temple is 1000 years old. It has been told that this temple has been built by Rajaraja Chola and the Lord Perumal who is here was his family deity.

The most important manifestation of Lord Vishnu in order to take away the evils from the earth to save his devotees is Narasimha Avatar. Many Narasimha temples are found all around South India. The most significant among them is Alagiya Narasimha Perumal temple in Ennayiram. This temple is the best example for the architecture of Chola Period consisting of places like *Idainazhi*, *Artha Mandapa*, *Mun Mandapa*, *Thiruchutru Maligai* and Compound Wall which has beautiful sculptures.

Inscriptions in the Temple

The inscriptions found in this temple have been inscribed during the period of Chola kings like Rajendra Chola I, Rajathiraja I, Kulothunga Chola I, Parakesari Tiribuvana Chakaravarthy Rajarajadeva, Mahamandaleswaran Rajarajendra Choladeva and the Vijayanagara kings like Achudevamaharaya and his son Sadasivamaharaya.

Vedic College

During the ancient times, only temples acted as the educational institutions. *Tirupadiyam* and *Tiruvaymoli* were taught there. The Vedic College was functioning at Alagiya Narasimha Perumal temple in Ennayiram during the period of Rajendra I (1014 - 1044 A.D). The Chola emperor donated 45 *Velis* of land for this college. The Vedic education was given to 340 students by 14 teachers in that college. The teachers of the college were given good salary and scholarships were given to students. The information about this Vedic College can be known from the inscriptions found in Alagiya Narasimha Perumal temple.

1. Students and Curriculum

In this college 75 students have learnt Rigveda, 75 students have learnt Yajurveda, 20 students have learnt Chandoga-sama, 20 students have learnt Talavakara-sama, 20 students have learnt Vajasaneya, 10 students have learnt Atharvaveda, 10 students have learnt Baudhayaniya grihya and kalpa and kathaka and totally 230 students (*brahmacharis*) and totally 270 students have learnt in this college including 40 students who have learnt

Rupavatara. Then totally 70 students (*sattira*) have received education which includes those who would listen to *Vyakarana* are 25 students, 35 students would listen to *Prabhakara*, 10 students would listen to *Vedanta*. Totally 340 students have studied in this college.

2. Number of Teachers

There were 3 professors to teach Rigveda, 3 professors to teach Yajurveda, 1 professor to teach Chandoga-sama, 1 professor to teach Talavakara-sama, 1 professor to teach Vajasaneya and 1 professor to teach Baudhayaniya grihya and kalpa and kathaka properly and totally 10 professors were appointed to teach these subjects in this college. 1 professor has been appointed to teach *Rupavatara*. Then 3 professors have been appointed to teach *Vyakarana*, *Prabhakara* and *Vedanta* respectively. Totally 14 professors were appointed in this college.

3. Scholarships for the Students

Scholarships were given to students in order to encourage education among students. 6 *nali* of paddy was given daily to 270 students who learnt Rigveda, Yajurveda, Chandoga-sama, Talavakara-sama, Vajasaneya, Baudhayaniya grihya and kalpa and kathaka respectively and the remaining 40 students learnt *Rupavatara*. 1 *kuruni* and 2 *nali* of paddy for a day and $\frac{1}{2}$ *kalanju* of gold for a person once in a year were given to the 70 students who listened to *Vyakarana*, *Prabhakara* and *Vedanta*. The Chola kings have encouraged the students who have successfully learnt and completed learning the three Vedas like Rig, Yajur and Sama respectively on “*Jayantiyashtami*” which was the birthday of Vennaikoothar (Krishna) by giving a ‘gold flower’ and a ‘gold ring’ to them.

4. Salaries of Teachers

3 *kuruni* of paddy was given for a day and $\frac{1}{2}$ *kalanju* of gold once in a year per person was given for the professors who taught Rigveda, Yajurveda, Chandoga-sama, Talavakara-sama, Vajasaneya, Baudhayaniya grihya and kalpa and kathaka respectively. Only 3 *kuruni* of paddy was given daily for the professors who taught *Rupavatara*. 1 *kalam* of paddy and 8 *kalanju* of gold for 8 chapters were given as the salary for the professors who taught *Vyakarana*. Those who taught *Prabhakara* were given 1 *kalam* of paddy for a day and 12 *kalanju* of gold for teaching 12 chapters of *Prabhakara*. Those who taught *Vedanta* were given only 1 *kalam* and 1 *tuni* of paddy. The professors who taught *Vedantas* were not given gold as the salary, because earning by teaching *Vedantas* was prohibited legally and morally.

5. Administration

The administration of this college was done by the village supervision committee. 30 *kalam* of paddy measured by the Rajarajan-*marakkal* were required for the professors who worked in this college and the students who studied in this college. 10,506 *kalam* of paddy and $6\frac{1}{2}$ *kalanju* of gold were required for a year. 45 *Veli* of land situated in Mambakkachcheri *alias* Pavittiramanikkanallur forming part of Anangur *alias* Rajarajanallur and Molakkudalur Purushanarayananallur was donated for the temple by the people of Rajaraja chaturvedimangalam with the permission of the king.

6. Hostel

The inscription found in this temple says that Rajendra Chola I had gone to North India and defeated the North Indian king and returned with a title called Gangaikondacholan and has built a hall named *Gangaikondacholan Mandapa* in Ennayiram. The hostel named Rajendracholan *Salai* was there in that hall which was near the college campus for the students and teachers. Apart from them, food was provided for 506 members including the Brahmins who learnt Vedas, the Brahmins who did not learn Vedas and *Sri Vaishnavas*. The

firewood which was required for the hostel was arranged by the greatmen incharge of the *ur-variya*m (the village supervision committee). Sugar and other things were given by the *Brahmins* and *Valnjiya* who were trading in the markets of this place. Apart from milk, curd and ghee were given to the temple; the remaining of these items were sent to the hostel.

Conclusion

Alagiya Narasimha Perumal temple is there in the village called Ennayiram. A college which taught Vedas was there in the campus of this temple during the period of Rajendra I. 340 students received education from that college. 14 professors worked in this college. The teachers taught Vedas like Rig and Yajur and Sutras such as Chandoga-sama, Talavakara-sama, Vajasaneya, Baudhayaniya grihya and kalpa and kathaka in this college. The professors who had worked in this college were given huge amount of salary and the scholarship was given to students who learnt in this college. It is not an exaggeration to say that Ennayiram Vedic College was one among the significant colleges which had a special place during the Chola period.

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